

Understanding Information Gaps on Preterm Birth for Expectant Mothers in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State Kaduna State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Keywords: Preterm Birth, Expectant Mothers, Preterm Birth Knowledge, Information Availability, Preterm Birth Information, Information Utilisation

Introduction: This study examined gaps in information utilisation on preterm birth for expectant mothers in Sabon Gari local government area of Kaduna State Kaduna State, Nigeria. Despite the essential role of information in preventing preterm birth, health management, improvement, and effective decision-making, expectant mothers lack general health information about their health conditions in the sub-Saharan African regions, specifically Nigeria. The level of awareness of available information on preterm birth needs improvement is low.

Methodology: Quantitative data was collected by using questionnaires for data collections. Out of the population of 2,019, the researcher employed a probability sampling technique and simple random sampling was used to sample 322 pregnant women for quantitative data collection. However, only 285 pregnant women consented and availed themselves of the study were used.

Findings/Results: The major type of preterm birth information available for women was birth control and antenatal information for pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in primary healthcare centres. However, child spacing and general health information could have been more extensive but underutilised. On the other hand, most of the pregnant women attending antenatal clinics have poor knowledge of preterm birth, lack of awareness and challenges related to accessing and use of preterm birth information.

Conclusion: Information on birth control, child spacing, and general health information received during antenatal visits by pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in primary healthcare centers can significantly contributes to safe child delivery.

Recommendation: Awareness of information on Preterm birth information must be provided and accessible by pregnant women to guide them in health decision-making. Knowledge of preterm birth should be improved through educational programs for community members.

Introduction

The incidence of preterm birth among pregnant women has been noted by scholars in developed and developing countries globally due to the high rate of mortality recorded by medical experts and social scientists (Changchang et al., 2018). According to the World Health Organization (2023), approximately 15 million babies are born preterm annually, accounting for 11% of all births worldwide; out of these fifteen million babies born, approximately one million die due to complications related to preterm birth, while many survivors face a lifetime challenge (WHO, 2023).

Preterm birth does not only affect infants and their families; it affects adults providing care for preterm infants, who may spend several months in hospital. Preterm birth has increasing cost implications for health services and affects women's active population in developed and developing countries worldwide. Preterm birth also comes with a lot of health challenges and complications, such as hypertension in pregnancy, stress-related physical activities, poor development, or information of some organs in the infants (congenital anomalies) as by researchers in Africa and sub-regions (Kwane et al., 2022).

As the leading cause of death of babies born before the due date of pregnancy among pregnant women worldwide, it is also a cause of disability and ill health later in life among infants (World Health Organization, 2023; Devi, 2018). The leading cause of death of babies born before the due date of pregnancy is among pregnant women worldwide. According to Devi (2018), it is also a cause of ill health later in life among infants. Knowledge of preterm birth and available information for prevention, healthcare management, health improvement and decision-making are critical. Preterm birth information must be made

available for expectant mothers for efficient child healthcare delivery.

Despite the essential role of information for preventing preterm birth, women need more understanding of information for health management, improvement and effective decision making, and general health information. Expectant mothers in the sub-Saharan African regions, specifically Nigeria, need to gain knowledge of available information on preterm utilisation. Most women tend to have challenges with access to and use of preterm birth information. There is difficulty in obtaining comprehensive and reliable information related to preterms in the sub-Saharan African regions.

The incidence of preterm birth is one of the prevalent global health issues that affect women's health and child delivery in African subregions, especially in Nigeria. To date, the challenge of preterm birth is a major concern in society today, most especially among women within the age range of childbirth in Nigeria. Despite the vital role of information in revealing the benefits of knowledge of preterm birth for expectant mothers, the problem persists. The reason could be their inability to access information to prepare them for safe delivery. There are several empirical studies on related subjects' prevalence and information use. Therefore, this study focuses on understanding preterm birth information for expectant mothers in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What type of preterm birth information is available to pregnant women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State Kaduna State, Nigeria?
2. What knowledge do pregnant women have about available preterm birth information in Sabon Gari Local

Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria?

3. What challenges do the women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State face in utilising preterm birth information?

Literature review

Discussions about the incidence of preterm birth and the risk factors surrounding the rate of mortality associated with it globally have been a primary concern among researchers. Studies show that Sub-Saharan *Africa* has the highest under-five mortality rate globally (Duraio et al., 2024; Tembo et al., 2024). As a global public health issue appr, approximately 15 million babies are born preterm annually, accounting for 11% of all births worldwide; out of these fifteen million babies born, approximately one million die due to complications related to preterm birth. At the same time, many survivors face lifetime challenges (WHO, 2023).

The effects on infants and their families providing care for preterm infants cannot be underestimated, given that the infant and the carers may spend several months in the hospital, with increasing cost implications for health services. Some of the *common problems associated with it include multiple pregnancies, infections and chronic conditions such as diabetes and high blood pressure, which could have been prevented with adequate knowledge and awareness of preterm birth information* (Derakhshi & Esmailnasab, 2014). *Also, the babies born in SGLGA usually suffer respiratory distress or laboured breathing, feeding difficulties, as well as hearing and vision problems, which result in anxiety, postpartum depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder, among others on the side of the mothers* (Raju et al., 2017).

Preterm birth knowledge relates to understanding the risk factors, preventive

measures, health interventions and complications associated with preterm delivery (Horvath et al., 2017). Knowledge of women's available preterm birth information is crucial for informed decision-making and to enable potential pregnant women to access relevant information and utilisation for safe delivery. Studies show that several factors are responsible for inadequate knowledge of preterm birth by pregnant women to support safe delivery (Levison et al., 2014).

The factors include a lack of knowledge of relevant information regarding preterm birth to support safe delivery. The procedures for safe delivery during pregnancy require that women possess adequate health knowledge, which can be made available by healthcare providers and other reliable sources (Chembe & Siziya, 2017; Pembe et al., 2009). Studies reported a poor understanding of preterm birth and complications that come with childbirth by women of childbearing age (Chembe & Siziya, 2017; Pembe et al., 2009).

Level of awareness about dangerous signs of pregnancy and labour, the norms, beliefs, and prevalence of cultural traditions in the community, where seeking permission from a male member of the family must be done before care can be sought (Chembe & Siziya, 2017; Pembe et al., 2009). The findings also showed that the temporal trends in PTB rates are highly heterogeneous among countries, but more information is needed regarding countries like China. Maternal education and prenatal care visits played essential roles in combating the trends of PTB rates among African women.

Expectant mothers are in dire need of adequate knowledge and information on preterm birth. Expectant mothers are women currently pregnant, expecting babies, and perhaps visiting healthcare facilities for medical care. Several women have acknowledged that they first learned about preterm birth during emergencies due to a lack of knowledge that

hindered their understanding of potential dangers involved and interventions, which sometimes contributed to hesitancy when risks were not well understood. (Chawanpaiboon et al., 2019).

Some women felt that their knowledge and ability to make informed decisions could be improved by clear communication, adequate information, time for discussion with their providers, and educational sessions with relevant materials. On the contrary, some women preferred to learn more about preterm birth and preterm birth management earlier in pregnancy. For instance, during antenatal care, women are allowed time to understand what may happen and how it may be managed. Women with previous experience of preterm birth agreed that they are aware of the danger and the likelihood of recurrence.

Knowledge of management and available options could give them greater confidence in making informed choices and negotiating their care. On the other hand, some women had limited knowledge of preterm birth and its causes. There were significant misconceptions, especially nutritional associations with preterm birth. Health education and awareness of valuable information are essential in unfolding the causes of preterm birth among women to help improve women's understanding of the condition in different regions in Nigeria and the rest of the world.

In Nigeria, the incidence of preterm birth and the mortality rate are alarming, given that the local norms, culture, and beliefs of the members of each community have an impact on the beliefs of the people.

The effective utilisation of preterm birth information relies on having accessible sources of information to ensure women access credible preterm birth information quickly; it is, therefore, essential that women, in general, are knowledgeable and aware of the danger of

preterm birth while information is made available in different formats for their knowledge consumption.

Meanwhile, preterm birth is prevalent based on the researcher's observation and preliminary investigation in some areas in Sabongari LGA. The researcher also observed that despite the importance of awareness and knowledge of the risk involved in preterm birth to ensure that individual pregnant women have a safe delivery, there is a significant gap in the studies investigating the knowledge of pregnant women on available preterm birth information among women in Sabon Gari Local government Area of Kaduna state. Could it be that women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State face many challenges in understanding the risk of preterm birth or have no adequate understanding of available information on preterm birth for utilisation? The study must investigate knowledge and understanding of the risks and available information on preterm birth in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey design using the quantitative approach in the data collection method, data analysis and the discussion of findings. Survey design is suitable for reaching out to the respondents and is helpful for large samples and groups of respondents (Ali et al., 2022); based on the submission by Fox et al. (2009) and Welman et al. (2005), it is the most economical design commonly used in social science and health-related research. The population of this study was two thousand nineteen (2,019) (pregnant women) attending antenatal clinics in the five selected health care in Sabon Gari Local Government area of Kaduna state. The sample size for this study was 322 (16%) pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in the Primary Healthcare centres in Sabon Gari Local Government. The

sample was drawn from the Research Advisory Table (Ruppel, 2008). Therefore, out of the population of 2,019, a sample of 322 pregnant women was drawn. The researcher employed a probability sampling technique using simple random to sample 322 pregnant women. Five hospitals were selected to represent the entire population; Healthcare centres with the most registered pregnant women were selected. The justification was that the sampling technique was economically advantageous to the researcher at the time of data collection. An instrument for data collection used was a questionnaire. The justifications for using questionnaires were to maximise the proportion of respondents answering the questions and to obtain accurate, relevant information for the survey. A self-developed questionnaire administered consists of close-ended questions to enable the researcher to analyse the data quantitatively (Shivaji, 2017; El-Sayyed, 2023), who opined that closed-ended questions allow the researcher to collect data that can be easily quantified. The questions were grouped into four sections: Section A – covers demographic information; Section B – covers types of information available on to pregnant women on preterm birth in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State; Section C – Knowledge possessed by pregnant women about available preterm birth information in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, and Section D- covers the Challenges faced by women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State face in utilising preterm birth information.

Face and content validation was used to validate the research data collection instrument. The validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by the two supervisors of the research work and two additional Senior Lecturers in the Department of Library and Information Science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Face validity ensures that the questionnaire covers the area of need in extracting the relevant data from the

respondents. A pilot study was conducted on ten (10) women attending the antenatal clinic in PHC Layin Sarki, Tudun Wada Zaria, which was not part of the study. The consistency and scale reliability of the instrument were obtained using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

The researcher provided informed consent for the study respondents with the approved letter of ethical clearances from the selected healthcare facilities where the data was collected. The letter was attached to the copies of the questionnaire to facilitate data collection. Five (5) research assistants from each healthcare centre were employed to collect data from the women and interpret the questionnaire in the Hausa language for those who do not understand English and those who cannot read and write. The Hausa Language was transcribed using google translate to English Language. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in their respective areas. This step was taken to ensure that the target respondents were reached and that the maximum return of questionnaires was achieved. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics (Frequency distribution, percentages, mean and standard deviation). A benchmark of 3.0 mean score was adopted to interpret and make decisions about the data collected for the research question on a Likert Scale.

RESULTS

Response Rate

A Three hundred and twenty-two (322) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in PHCs in Sabon Gari local government of Kaduna State, out of which 285 copies were duly completed and found worthy of analysis. The justification for distributing more questionnaires was to obtain the sample size suggested by the Research Advisory Table 2006. This high response can be attributed to

the persistent follow-ups and the research assistants' familiarity with the pregnant women. The response rate of the respondents from their

health care centres and marital status are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table.1: Present the Summary of Descriptive Analysis of Response Rate from the Wards/ Primary Health Centres

S/N	Wards/ Primary Health Center	Copies of questionnaire distributed	Copies of questionnaire filled and returned	% of copies of questionnaire filled and returned
1	Basawa ward/ Primary Health center	48	41	12.73
2	Jushi ward/ Primary Health center	69	58	18.01
3	Dogarawa ward/ Primary Health center	46	39	12.11
4	Samaru ward/ Primary Health center	97	90	27.95
5	Muchia ward/ Primary Health center	62	57	17.70
TOTAL		322	285	88.5

Table 1 shows the response rate of the respondents in the primary health centres, and the table reveals that three hundred and twenty-two (322) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. However, 285 (88.5%) responses were completed, returned, and used for the analysis. The analysis shows that Samaru Ward/Primary healthcare center have the highest number of respondents (N=90; 27.95%), followed by Jushi Ward Primary health care centre (N=58; 81.01%), and Muchia Primary Health centre (N=57, 17.70%). Other primary health centre includes Basawa Ward

(N=41; 12.73%) and Dogarawa Ward (N=39; 12.11%). Interestingly, the high response rate was attributed to the frequent follow-up by the researcher and the research's assistants to retrieve the distributed copies of questionnaire.

Respondents' Marital Status

Data related to marital status were collected from respondents and analyzed using descriptive method of analysis involving frequencies and percentages. The table.2 provides the summary of the analysis and presentation.

Table 2: Marital Status of the Respondents

	Marital Status	Frequency (F)	Percentages (%)
A	Single mothers	10	3.51
B	Married	262	91.93
C	Divorced	13	4.56
	Total	285	100

Table 2 presents the descriptive analysis of respondents' marital status. The analysis shows that most respondents were married (N=262; 91.93%), followed by divorced respondents (N=13; 4.56%). Others were single mothers (N=10; 3.51%). The result indicated that many respondents were married women during data collection.

Types of Preterm Birth Information Available to Pregnant Women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

The quantitative data collected based on the types of preterm birth information were collected from the respondents. The researcher used a descriptive analysis involving frequency and percentages were used. The summary of the analysis was presented in table 3.

Table 3: Types of Preterm Birth information available to Pregnant Women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State

	Items Statements	Frequency(F)	Percentages (%)
A	General health information	9	3.16
B	Information on birth control	140	49.12
C	Antenatal information	90	31.58
D	Postnatal information	11	3.86
E	Information on healthy timing and spacing of pregnancy	35	12.28
	Total	285	100

Table 3 presents respondents' opinions on the types of preterm birth information. Most of the respondents (N140=49.12%) indicated that health information on birth control was available, followed by antenatal information (N=90; 31.58%) and information on healthy timing and spacing of pregnancy (N=35; 12.28%). Other available information indicated by respondents includes postnatal information (N=11; 3.86%); the lowest in that category was general health information (N=9; 3.16%).

Knowledge of Pregnant Women on the Available Preterm Birth Information at Health Care Centers in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State

Quantitative data were collected based on the available preterm birth information. Descriptive analysis involving frequency and percentages was used. The summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Analysis of the Knowledge of Pregnant Women on the Available Preterm Birth Information at Health Care Centers in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State

	Items Statements	Frequency(F)	Percentages (%)
A	Knowledgeable	66	23.16
B	Not Knowledgeable	219	76.84
	Total	285	100

Table 4 reveals the opinions of respondents regarding the knowledge of pregnant women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State are, on the available preterm birth information. Findings show that most respondents (N=219; 76.84%) needed to know more about preterm birth information. On the contrary, a few respondents (N=66; 23.16%) were knowledgeable about preterm birth information in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This finding agreed with Norton et al. (2016), who, in their study, stated that some women had limited knowledge of preterm birth and its causes, making it difficult

for them to utilise available preterm birth information. The study is also in conformity with Pembe et al. (2009), the study reported that women of childbearing age had poor knowledge of preterm birth, its complications and appropriate care. This was attributed to the low level of awareness about dangerous signs of pregnancy and labour as well as the prevalence of cultural traditions in the community, where seeking permission from a male member (or being accompanied by a male member) of the family must be done before care can be sought.

Challenges the Pregnant Women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State Faced in Utilising Preterm Birth Information

Table 5: Present the Summary of Descriptive Analysis on the Challenges the Pregnant Women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State Faced in Utilising Preterm Birth Information

	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mea n	SD
S/ N	Challenges Faced by Women Regarding Access and Use of Preterm Birth Information						
	Frequency (%)						
A	Religious belief is a challenge to access and	109(38.25)	118(41.40)	15(5.26)	26(9.12)	17(5.96)	3.97 1.99

	use of preterm birth information							
B	Financial constraints are a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information	205(71.92)	72(25.26)	3(1.05)	4(1.40)	1(0.35)	4.67	2.16
C	Cultural traditions are a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information	179(62.81)	92(32.28)	1(0.35)	8(2.81)	5(1.75)	4.52	2.13
D	Difficulty in obtaining comprehensive and reliable information is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information	163(57.19)	107(37.54)	1(0.35)	6(2.11)	8(2.81)	4.44	2.10
E	Poor knowledge of preterm birth / Lack of Awareness is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information	185(64.91)	79(27.71)	3(1.05)	10(3.51)	8(2.81)	4.48	2.11
F	Family opposition is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information	17(5.96)	20(7.02)	14(4.91)	158(55.44)	76(26.67)	2.10	1.45

Key: SA: Strongly Agreed, UD: Undecided, SD: Strongly Disagreed, A: Agreed, D: Disagreed SD: Standard Deviation

Table 5 presents the analysis of respondents' opinions on the challenges pregnant women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State faced in utilising preterm birth information. The analysis revealed that all the items were retained with a mean above the decision mean of 3.00, except the last item with a mean of 2.10, which is lower than the decision mean of 3.00. The item in column 'b' revealed that the respondents agreed that financial constraints are a challenge to access and use preterm birth information (4.67), and column 'c' revealed that the respondents agreed that cultural tradition is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information (4.52), item 'e' revealed that the respondents agreed that, poor knowledge of preterm birth/lack of awareness is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information (4.48), followed by the item in column 'd', the respondents agreed that the difficulty in obtaining comprehensive and reliable information is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information (4.44), in item 'a' the respondents agreed that religious belief is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information (3.97), while in item 'f' the respondents were agreed that, family opposition is a challenge to access and use of preterm birth information with mean of (2.10).

Discussion of findings

This current study investigated how women in Sabon Gari local government of Kaduna State of Nigeria utilise information on preterm birth. The study sought to identify the type of preterm birth information available to pregnant women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, to examine the knowledge of pregnant women on available preterm birth information and challenges encountered with using information by expectant women in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna

State, Relevant and related literature was reviewed during the study.

Based on the research question, information on birth control and antenatal information were the significant types of information available for pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in the primary healthcare centres in Sabon Gari local government area of Kaduna state, followed by antenatal information and information on healthy timing and spacing of pregnancy and the lowest in that category was general health information. The findings signified the negative implications of the lack of adequate health information focusing on preterm birth for women in most of the health facilities within Zaria Metropolis. Information on birth control and antenatal information was the general subject of discussion and was mostly available and obtainable in all healthcare centres. However, antenatal and postnatal information that is paramount for women and child delivery is not readily available in healthcare centres.

These findings align with Ogunmodede et al. (2013), who acknowledged that the information required to effect changes in women's health status is either insufficient or unavailable. Hence, the decision made at any given time depends mainly on the type of information that is made available to the user. This finding agreed with Cunningham-Myrie et al. (2008) and Oladipo (2014) that there are deficiencies in the quality and availability of health information for women; as such, utilisation of health services is related to availability, quality, and cost of the services as well as social structure, knowledge, health beliefs and personal characteristics of those using the services.

Based on research question two, findings show that most of the respondents (Most of the

pregnant women attending antenatal clinic in Sabon Gari local government of Kaduna state were not knowledgeable about preterm birth information and therefore did not utilise it. This finding agreed with Chembe and Siziya (2017), who, in their study, stated that some women had limited knowledge of preterm birth and its causes, making it difficult for them to utilise available preterm birth information. The study is also in conformity with Pembe Urassa et al. (2009), whose study reported that women of childbearing age had poor knowledge of preterm birth, its complications and appropriate care. The finding was attributed to the low level of awareness about dangerous signs of pregnancy and labour as well as the prevalence of cultural traditions in the community, where seeking permission from a male member (or being accompanied by a male member) of the family must be done before care can be sought.

Based on research question three, findings revealed that most of the challenges faced by the pregnant women were due to their religious beliefs, financial constraints, cultural traditions, difficulty in obtaining comprehensive and reliable information, poor knowledge of preterm birth and lack of awareness of the challenges faced by pregnant women in Sabon Gari local government regarding access and use of preterm birth information. The finding agreed with Muoghalu (2010), who, in his study, found that many women are illiterates, which affects their knowledge and exposure level. Also, their level of income and all these impinge on their nutritional status and affect their ability to exercise their rights as human beings.

Conclusion

The findings of this current study revealed that knowledge of preterm birth plays an essential role in exposing the risks associated with preterm birth among pregnant women. The study shows that understanding the risk factors and knowledge of preventive measures, health

interventions, and complications associated with preterm child delivery play a crucial role in health management, health improvement, and patient decision-making. This study established that information on birth control and antenatal information was essential for pregnant women attending antenatal clinics and was available in the primary healthcare centres in Sabon Gari's local government area of Kaduna state. Knowledge of preterm birth and available information was scarce among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in the primary healthcare centres in Sabon Gari's local government area of Kaduna state. Few pregnant women know preterm birth information and, therefore, were not available for them for utilisation.

This study established that most of the pregnant women in Sabon Gari local government have no access to preterm birth information due to challenges related to religious belief, financial constraints, cultural traditions, difficulty in obtaining comprehensive and reliable information, poor knowledge of preterm birth and lack of awareness. The findings can guide the development of a shared decision-making tool for parents and clinicians for a mode of delivery in extremely preterm breech singletons, enabling patient-centred care. Women can use knowledge of preterm birth to make healthcare decisions for themselves and their children.

This study provides insight into how providers can share information, utilise informed consent, and provide respectful care for women during pregnancy and birth care. The study had some constraints associated with the nature of the study population. The constraint centred on only pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in PHCs in Sabon Gari, the local government of Kaduna state. Therefore, the time and availability of the respondents are significant limitations. Despite the constraints, the findings from this study can only be generalised within the context of the study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Knowledge of preterm birth should be improved through educational programs. It should be provided by the hospitals, community centres, or online platforms, while the relevant stakeholders in the healthcare sector, such as the Ministry of Health, state and local government authorities in conjunction with the Hospitals in Kaduna State, should engage and educate the women on better ways to access and acquire knowledge of preterm birth health information, antenatal information and postnatal information.
2. In collaboration with healthcare centres, the local government authority should create avenues for promoting health information using posters displayed in hospitals or even going beyond the hospital premises to places such as markets and schools and having health practitioners address health issues during pregnancy. Moreover, this information must be available in different formats, such as print, audio, and online.
3. There is a need to create awareness and educate women about the danger signs of pregnancy and labor, thereby encouraging them to utilise preterm birth information available to them.

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